

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
SUSTAINABLE CITIES &
COMMUNITIES (ICSCC-2020)

7-8 FEBRUARY, 2020
at GD Goenka University, Gurugram

Organized by:
School of Basic & Applied Sciences and School of Engineering
GD Goenka University, Gurugram Sohna Road, Haryana 122103

In collaboration with
Arizona State University, USA

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BUILDING & CITIES

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Published: 2020

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